

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CONCEPT OF THEORETICAL TRAINING IN SPORTS

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Annotation: It has been determined that in modern conditions of the functioning of sports, the concept of theoretical training in sports acts as an independent subject for scientific knowledge and the implementation of a series of consistent studies. They should be aimed at verifying its main provisions. This will ensure the full functioning of the athletes' training system and will be reflected in the results of the competitive activities of athletes in various groups of sports.

Key words: concept, theoretical training, sports.

Introduction. The creation of new theoretical concepts must always precede the practical solution of any consciously defined problem. In sports activities, without an established system of knowledge that answers a number of pressing questions, in particular - what and how to do, what the results of movements should be, an athlete is unlikely to be able to rationally and effectively perform the exercise and generally realize the level of functional readiness [1, 3, 5 , 8].

In sports, the need to update the training system as a whole and its individual components, in particular theoretical training, is permanent. However, despite some attempts at scientific research in the direction of theoretical training of athletes [4, 6, 11], in terms of scientific and methodological information in the field of physical culture and sports, there is no fundamental research on theoretical training in sports. Existing scientific data on the knowledge system for the transfer and formation of the sports pedagogical process among participants does not fully satisfy the social demand that takes place at the present stage of sports development [2, 7, 9].

Theoretical training in sports acts as a relatively independent side in the field of the structural process of training athletes. It has its expression both in the general structure of the training system for athletes at different stages (from the initial training stage to the stage of retirement from sports), and in different components - training, competition and renewal [10, 12].

Various aspects of the system of training athletes are quite widely represented in the scientific research of specialists in the field of physical culture and sports. They are associated both with the solution of scientific and practical problems, and scientific and applied problems in relation to physical, technical, tactical, and mental training [14, 15]. At the same time, a well-developed array of scientific information in the theory and practice of sports allowed us to assert that there is no concept of theoretical training in sports as a whole in the historical aspect and at the present stage of the functioning of sports [13, 16].

In connection with the identified contradictions between the existence of theoretical training as a relatively independent side in the system of long-term improvement of athletes, the reflection of this in training programs for sports and the lack of proper scientific and methodological justification, we have formed an urgent scientific and applied problem of creating a conceptual foundation for theoretical training in sports [17, 18].

The concept of theoretical training in sports acts as: a system of views on the educational and training process with its inherent holistic-resultative aspects of the transfer and formation of specific knowledge at all stages of multi-year improvement of athletes; as a way of interpreting the pedagogical process in sports through understanding and a fundamental focus on solving the main tasks of achieving the maximum individual result and personality formation; the idea of the theory of theoretical training, which is reflected in the practice of training athletes.

The presentation of this theory can be based on the identification of a set of conclusions and conclusions that reflect the objectively existing relationships and connections between the objective phenomena of the system of theoretical training

in sports. The system of theoretical training is a set of entities, subject-object relations for the formation of special knowledge and connections between the participants of the pedagogical process, isolated from the environment of sports activities for a certain time in order to ensure a comprehensive study of the relevant side of the training of athletes.

In order to substantiate the concept of theoretical training in sports, we made a formal check on the compliance of this aspect of training with the main properties of the system. It has been established that, based on its basic properties, theoretical training has every reason to be considered as a system. Thus, theoretical training in sports is a set of elements that under certain conditions can be considered as systems. This is confirmed by the fact that it is characterized by function principles, methods, means, implementation conditions, etc., which can act as independent systems.

In theoretical training, there are significant connections between elements and (or) their properties, which are superior in terms of the power (strength) of the connection between these elements and elements that are not part of this system. Essential connections are those that determine the integration properties of the system in a regular, necessary manner. The explanation for this is a set of significant functional connections between the components of the theoretical training system (principles, goal, tasks, implementation provisions), which interact with other aspects of training athletes (physical, technical, tactical, mental), but have significantly lower efficiency in within the limits of their implementation.

According to experts in the general methodology of scientific research, this property distinguishes the system (theoretical training) from a simple conglomerate and separates it from the environment (sports activity) in the form of a complete object.

Another property that allows us to consider theoretical training in sports as a system is the presence of a certain organization, which is manifested in a decrease in the degree of uncertainty of the system in comparison with the entropy of system-forming factors that determine the possibility of creating a system. This does not

indicate that the arrangement of the factors that form the system of theoretical training with the help of the development of the concept, as the idea of the theory, makes it possible to implement the goal-resultative orientation of the pedagogical process in the training of athletes with its orientation towards achieving the maximum result and, at the same time, the formation of the personality at a higher level of efficiency compared to their individual influences.

In addition, the existence of integration properties characteristic of the system as a whole, but not specific to any of its elements individually, is inherent in theoretical training. This indicates that none of the elements of the theoretical training system can fully determine this system. However, by combining these elements, it acquires new evolutionary features with a higher level of implementation power.

Taking into account the opinions of specialists makes it possible to interpret the system (elements, connections, subsystems) of theoretical training by origin as natural (living, social). This is explained by the fact that this system contains elements and their connections related to the direct participants of the social phenomenon - sports in all forms of its existence and at various stages of the multi-year improvement of athletes in real time of their reflection.

Thus, the concept of theoretical training in sports is presented as a set of elements with connections at different levels of the organization. In the successive steps of the scientific and methodological justification of the author's concept of theoretical training in sports, we see the need to interpret the doctrine of principles, forms and methods, which are its integral elements. It is worth noting that consideration of the author's concept of theoretical training must be carried out taking into account its structural and hierarchical levels: "prerequisites", "basic", "implementation", "result". The level of "prerequisites" of the concept of theoretical training is represented by the system of training athletes, its target-resultative orientation and guiding principles of pedagogical and educational and training processes.

In addition, the level of "realization" of the concept of theoretical training is determined by the presence of a block of elements of the system of theoretical training in sports, which is represented by its guiding provisions (principles), functions and tasks. In accordance with them, implementation provisions are being formed regarding the formation of theoretical preparedness of athletes as a result of the corresponding type of training. Actually, implementation provisions are represented by such low-level elements as methods, means, forms, conditions for the implementation of theoretical training and its control. They, in combination and taking into account the divisions of training athletes and stages of multi-year training, allow to develop and compose differentiated programs of theoretical training (goal, task, direct implementation and control).

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